

A COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF ESP COURSE IMPLEMENTATION USING THE CIPP MODEL

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ABSTRACT

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is a form of language instruction designed to equip learners with the linguistic knowledge and skills required for specific academic and professional contexts. The effectiveness of ESP programs depends not only on curriculum content, but also on needs analysis, instructional materials, teaching methodology, implementation quality, and the alignment between intended and achieved outcomes. For this reason, the systematic evaluation of ESP programs has become increasingly important. This study aims to evaluate the implementation of Professional English I and Professional English II courses for accounting and finance students using the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) evaluation model. The participants were students enrolled in two ESP courses at a private university. The ESP-1 evaluation report included 157 second-year accounting students, while the ESP-2 evaluation report covered 117 third-year students majoring in Accounting and Finance. The study employed a document-based comparative evaluation design using descriptive analysis. It sought not only to present the existing evaluation results, but also to examine the pedagogical progression and distinctive emphases of the two courses. The findings reveal high levels of student satisfaction and strong alignment among course objectives, instructional materials, and professional learning outcomes. The integration of digital tools and learner-centered teaching approaches also contributed to positive results. However, the analysis identified oral communication and presentation skills as areas requiring further improvement. Findings indicate that the courses effectively promote the development of professional English competence while also revealing a continued need to enhance communicative competence through future curriculum improvement efforts.

Keywords: CIPP model; course evaluation; Professional English; course implementation; needs analysis.

Introduction

The 1960s marked an important period of change in English language education. As industry expanded, technology advanced, and global connections increased, the demand for English in specialized academic and professional settings grew rapidly. It was within this changing context that English for Specific Purposes (ESP) emerged as a distinct branch of language teaching. Unlike general English instruction, ESP was developed to respond more directly to learners' specific academic, occupational, and professional goals. In this sense, ESP places emphasis not simply on learning English as a general subject, but on using English as a practical tool within a particular field. By linking language instruction to learners' real needs, ESP makes learning more purposeful, relevant, and applicable (Fitria, 2020). Although ESP courses are designed to meet learners' professional needs, evidence of their effective implementation remains limited. Systematic evaluation is therefore necessary to examine the alignment of course objectives, resources, teaching processes, and learning outcomes, beyond student satisfaction alone. Ongoing evaluation also helps monitor program effectiveness and guide necessary improvements. As globalization and specialization continue to grow, the importance of ESP in academic and professional contexts becomes increasingly significant. (Muminova, 2025). Evaluating both student progress and the courses they take has long been a central concern in education. In ESP courses, evaluation is particularly important because these courses are built around specific objectives. The main challenge is to support effective learning by

aligning course content with learners' needs, using relevant and authentic materials, applying learner-centered methods, and continuously refining instruction to help students develop the language skills required in their academic or professional settings (Latifaj, 2025). Needs analysis, or needs assessment, has long served as a fundamental component of ESP practice and is expected to remain central to future ESP work. Since emerging in the 1970s, it has developed into a widely recognized framework that has received substantial attention from researchers and practitioners in both ESP and ESL (2023).

Thus, this study adopted Stufflebeam's CIPP model, a widely used framework in English language program evaluation that offers comprehensive insight into both program strengths and areas for improvement.

Literature Review

Despite the growing importance of ESP, studies evaluating ESP courses remain limited. Addressing this gap, Handan Çelik examined tertiary students' end-of-course evaluations of an ESP course offered in the Banking Department of a state university in Turkey. Using a survey design, the study collected both quantitative and qualitative data from 96 students on the ESP instructor, course materials, course content, and suggested areas for improvement (Çelik, 2018).

Mentari Putri Wulan ((March, 2026)) and his co-authors studied the development, trends, applications, and research gaps of the CIPP (Context, Input, Process, Product) Evaluation Model in education. Using a systematic literature review guided by PRISMA 2020 and based on a structured Scopus search, 22 relevant studies were selected through the stages of identification,

screening, eligibility, and inclusion. The findings show that the CIPP model remains a widely applied and adaptable evaluation framework across diverse educational settings, including primary, secondary, higher, and professional education.

In her study (Mičinová, 2023) evaluates the course project assignment in terms of affective outcomes, such as students' perceptions of its benefits and their experience of conducting research, cognitive outcomes related to language and subject knowledge, and behavioural outcomes, including skills development and engagement. Data were obtained through content analysis of students' diaries, project presentations, written reports, and a post-project survey. Similarly, (Mimin Aminah1, 2025) evaluated the implementation of an ESP program for engineering students at a private university in West Java, Indonesia, using the CIPP model. Their findings highlighted the need to align curriculum design, teaching strategies, and resources with learners' needs, while also demonstrating the value of the CIPP model as a comprehensive framework for ESP program evaluation. As noted by Chun-Fu Chen (2009) the CIPP model has been widely used in educational evaluation across different disciplines and contexts. Previous studies have applied it to assess curriculum effectiveness, program relevance, and areas for improvement. For example, Huang (2001) used the model to evaluate a chemical engineering curriculum in Taiwan and found that, although the program generally developed the skills and qualities required by graduates, several course areas needed revision. Wong (2002) applied the CIPP model to a computer studies program in Hong Kong and reported that the program met industry needs and program objectives, while still requiring some operational improvements. Similarly, Umit (2004) used the model to evaluate a Turkish language teaching program in Belarus and found that it only partially met stakeholder needs. Other studies have also employed the CIPP model in evaluating programs in mechanical engineering, banking and insurance, reading instruction, nursing, and coach training, demonstrating its broad applicability in educational settings.

Theoretical Framework: CIPP Model

The CIPP model is a comprehensive framework that evaluates programs through four dimensions—

Figure 1 CIPP model

Methodology

This study employed a document-based evaluative analysis using two course implementation reports: one

context, input, process, and product—and offers the advantage of identifying program goals, implementation quality, and opportunities for improvement simultaneously. This model views evaluation as an ongoing process that supports planning and change within regular institutional programs, rather than as a one-time activity for a single project or study. Unlike traditional models that mainly focus on final outcomes, the CIPP model provides a systematic and flexible approach that supports informed decision-making at every stage of a program (Huang, 2025). In contemporary education, evaluation is no longer seen simply as a way to measure learning outcomes or students' cognitive performance through standardized tests. Rather, it is understood as a broader and more systematic process that considers policy, institutional context, resources, implementation, and program outcomes. This shift reflects the view that educational quality cannot be explained by outcomes alone, but by the interaction of multiple elements within the educational system (March, 2026). Tessmer (1993) explains that the four dimensions of the CIPP model—context, input, process, and product—can be used for both formative and summative evaluation. The model serves a formative function when it gathers information for ongoing improvement, and a summative function when it assesses completed activities, interprets overall results, and supports accountability.

Within this framework, *context evaluation* examines the environment in which the program operates and considers whether its goals respond to actual needs. It also helps identify unmet needs and missed opportunities. *Input evaluation* focuses on planning by reviewing the resources, strategies, and institutional capacity available to achieve the program's goals. In this way, it helps determine the most appropriate course of action. *Process evaluation* looks at how the program is implemented and whether activities are carried out effectively and efficiently, while also providing feedback for improvement. Finally, *product evaluation* examines the outcomes of the program, including both intended and unintended results, to determine whether its goals were achieved and whether the program should be maintained, revised, or discontinued (Ulumi, 2016).

for Professional English I and one for Professional English II. The Professional English I report covered the 2024–2025 academic year, while the Professional English II report covered the 2025–2026 academic year.

The reports included student survey findings, teacher reflections on instructional practices, comments on course strengths and limitations, and comparative evidence from inbound and outbound testing. The survey items from both reports were reorganized and interpreted according to the four dimensions of the CIPP model.

For the purpose of analysis, items related to course goals, clarity, and relevance were categorized under Context. Items concerning instructional materials, assessment tools, resources, and learning platforms were grouped under Input. Items describing implementation, feedback, student guidance, and task alignment were treated as Process indicators. Finally, all items reflecting improvement in student skills, competencies, and measurable progress were analyzed under Product. This analytical framework made it possible to synthesize the two reports into a coherent evaluation structure.

Participants

The participants were students enrolled in the two ESP courses. According to the ESP-1 evaluation report, 157 second-level students with an accounting-related background participated in the survey. According to the ESP-2 evaluation report, 117 third-level students from accounting- and finance-related classes participated in the survey. In both cases, the participants were students studying discipline-specific English within the broader context of accounting and finance education.

Instrument and Data Collection

The main instrument used in the original reports was a course evaluation questionnaire designed to assess students' perceptions of course implementation and learning outcomes. The questionnaire items addressed such areas as clarity of learning expectations, alignment of content with course objectives, appropriateness of instructional materials, usefulness of digital learning tools, clarity of assessment, feedback, and perceived improvement in academic and professional skills. In addition to the quantitative questionnaire data, the reports also included qualitative comments from students and teachers, as well as summary evidence from inbound-outbound test performance.

Analytical Framework

For the purposes of this study, the original survey items from the two reports were analytically reclassified according to the four dimensions of the CIPP

model. Items related to the clarity, relevance, and alignment of learning goals were classified under Context. Items concerning instructional resources, textbooks, assessment rubrics, and digital learning support were categorized as Input. Items focusing on feedback, task guidance, and implementation-related instructional processes were grouped under Process. Finally, items reflecting students' perceived improvement in knowledge, skills, and discipline-related competencies were classified under Product. Because the two original questionnaires were not fully identical, the items were further organized into directly comparable items and course-specific items in order to ensure analytical clarity and avoid forced one-to-one equivalence between non-matching indicators.

Results

The data were analyzed through descriptive comparative analysis. First, the mean percentage scores reported for each survey item were extracted from the two evaluation reports. Second, the items were grouped according to the researcher's CIPP-based classification. Third, conceptually similar items across ESP-1 and ESP-2 were compared in order to examine shared implementation strengths and differences. Finally, course-specific items were interpreted separately to identify the distinctive pedagogical emphasis of each course. Qualitative comments from students and teachers were used to support and contextualize the interpretation of the quantitative findings, particularly in relation to the strengths, challenges, and suggested improvements identified in the two reports. To strengthen the analytical rigor of the evaluation, the survey items from ESP-1 and ESP-2 were reorganized according to the four dimensions of the CIPP model, namely Context, Input, Process, and Product. The dimension-level means were calculated based on the researcher's CIPP-based reclassification of the original course evaluation items.

Part A includes only those survey items that were conceptually comparable across ESP-1 and ESP-2. Part B presents course-specific items that appeared in only one of the two evaluation reports. The CIPP categories reflect researcher-led analytical reclassification of the original survey items, while the mean scores were taken from the original course evaluation reports.

Table 1

Comparative Classification of ESP-1 and ESP-2 Course Evaluation Questions According to the CIPP Model with Mean Scores

Part A. Directly Comparable Items

CIPP Dimension	Evaluation Focus	ESP-1 Item	Mean (%)	ESP-2 Item	Mean (%)
Context	Clarity of learning expectations	What I was expected to learn in this course was clear to me.	94.06	What I was expected to learn in this course was clear to me.	93.70
Context	Alignment of content with course objectives	The content of each topic was aligned with the overall objectives of the course.	94.48	The content of each topic was aligned with the overall objectives of the course.	96.00
Input	Integration of theory with learning activities	Theoretical instruction was well connected with independent work.	92.78	Theoretical understanding was well connected with seminar, laboratory, or practical work.	92.00
Input	Clarity of assessment methods and rubrics	The assessment methods and rubrics were clear and understandable.	94.06	The assessment methods and rubrics were clear, understandable, and appropriate to the intended learning outcomes.	91.40
Input	Alignment of instructional materials	The main textbook was consistent with the course content.	95.54	The instructional content was consistent with the main textbook and the curriculum.	95.10
Input	Communication of assessment criteria	The assessment criteria were clearly explained at the beginning of the course.	95.12	The assessment criteria were clearly explained at the beginning of the course.	93.00
Input	Usefulness of digital learning support	The E-mandakh online learning system was useful and easy to use for learning.	90.38	The E-mandakh online learning system was useful and easy to use for learning.	91.30
Process	Role of formative assessment and feedback	Formative assessment and feedback motivated me to prepare for and complete subsequent tasks.	93.63	Formative assessment and feedback motivated me to prepare for and complete subsequent tasks.	90.80
Process	Clarity of task expectations	It was clear what students were expected to do in the course.	94.06	It was clear what students were expected to do in the course.	91.10

As shown in Table 3, both ESP-1 and ESP-2 received consistently high mean scores across the CIPP dimensions, indicating positive student perceptions of course implementation in both stages of the program. Within the Context dimension, both courses were rated highly in terms of clarity of learning expectations and alignment between lesson content and overall course objectives. In particular, the item addressing alignment of content with course objectives received a mean score of 94.48 in ESP-1 and 96.00 in ESP-2, suggesting

strong curricular coherence across both courses. In the Input dimension, students in both courses reported high levels of satisfaction with instructional materials, assessment transparency, and digital learning support. The strongest input-related item in both courses was the alignment of instructional materials with curriculum expectations, with mean scores of 95.54 for ESP-1 and 95.10 for ESP-2. Similarly, assessment criteria explained at the beginning of the course were rated positively in both courses, although ESP-1 showed slightly

higher scores than ESP-2 across most comparable input indicators.

Part B: Course-Specific Items

Course	CIPP Dimension	Evaluation Focus	Course-Specific Item	Mean (%)	Interpretation
ESP-1	Product	Inquiry and presentation skills	My ability to conduct inquiry, prepare presentations, and present findings improved.	89.53	ESP-1 placed clear emphasis on foundational academic communication and presentation competence.
ESP-1	Product	Information-handling skills	My ability to collect, process, and use information improved.	95.02	This was one of the strongest ESP-1 outcomes, highlighting growth in academic information literacy.
ESP-1	Product	Professional terminology	My ability to recognize and translate profession-related terminology improved.	93.42	ESP-1 emphasized disciplinary vocabulary development and translation competence.
ESP-1	Product	Oral interaction and discourse	My ability to engage in dialogue and express main ideas within a relevant discourse improved.	89.96	ESP-1 included explicit emphasis on basic oral communication and discourse-level expression.
ESP-2	Process	Alignment of term papers/assignments with the curriculum	Term papers and assignments were aligned with the course curriculum.	91.60	ESP-2 more explicitly evaluated the curricular coherence of assignments during implementation.
ESP-2	Product	Technology use in learning	My ability to use technological advances in learning improved.	92.00	ESP-2 highlighted students' growth in technology-supported learning competence.
ESP-2	Product	Accounting-related comprehension and application	My ability to read, understand, and use accounting-related information in everyday practice improved.	92.80	ESP-2 emphasized applied comprehension of discipline-specific content.
ESP-2	Product	Profession-related calculation skills	My ability to perform profession-related calculations improved.	91.10	ESP-2 assessed field-specific practical competence beyond general language development.

In terms of the Process dimension, formative feedback and clarity of task expectations were positively evaluated in both courses, indicating that students generally perceived the teaching-learning process as well organized and supportive. However, ESP-1 obtained somewhat higher ratings than ESP-2 on both comparable process indicators. For example, the motivational role of formative assessment and feedback was rated 93.63 in ESP-1 compared with 90.80 in ESP-2, while clarity of task expectations was rated 94.06 in ESP-1 and 91.10 in ESP-2. In addition, ESP-2 included a dis-

tinct process-related item on the alignment of independent assignments with the curriculum, which received a mean score of 91.60, reflecting the greater emphasis of the second course on structured independent work.

The Product dimension revealed both shared outcomes and developmental differences between the two courses. In both ESP-1 and ESP-2, teamwork was among the relatively lower-rated outcomes, with mean scores of 89.38 and 90.20, respectively, although both values still indicate generally positive perceptions. At

the same time, the course-specific product items suggest a developmental progression from foundational to applied professional competence. ESP-1 showed strong outcomes in information-handling skills ($M = 95.02$) and professional terminology development ($M = 93.42$), whereas ESP-2 showed strong outcomes in accounting-related comprehension and application ($M = 92.80$), technology-supported learning ($M = 92.00$), profession-related calculations ($M = 91.10$), and financial reporting in English ($M = 91.60$). Taken together, these results suggest that ESP-1 primarily supported the development of foundational academic and disciplinary English competences, while ESP-2 extended these competences into more specialized and profession-oriented applications.

Discussion

The findings suggest that both ESP-1 and ESP-2 were implemented effectively across the main CIPP dimensions, with students reporting positive perceptions of course clarity, curriculum alignment, learning resources, and assessment transparency. This supports earlier studies by Çelik (Çelik, 2018) and Aminah et al. (Mimin Aminah1, 2025), which emphasized the importance of well-structured ESP instruction and the alignment of curriculum, teaching strategies, and resources with learner needs. The results also reveal a clear developmental progression between the two courses, as ESP-1 mainly supported foundational academic and disciplinary English skills, whereas ESP-2 extended these toward more applied professional competencies, consistent with (Mićimová, 2023) emphasis on the cognitive and practical value of ESP tasks. At the same time, lower ratings for teamwork and oral communication in both courses indicate that spoken communicative competence remains underdeveloped, echoing prior CIPP-based studies summarized by (Chen, 2009), (Huang, 2025) which showed that even effective programs often require targeted improvement in specific areas. Overall, the findings confirm that the two courses function as complementary stages within a coherent ESP curriculum and further support the usefulness of the CIPP model as a framework for identifying both strengths and areas for future improvement.

Conclusion

This study employed the CIPP model to evaluate the implementation of ESP-1 and ESP-2 through the four dimensions of context, input, process, and product. The findings demonstrate that both courses were implemented effectively, with evidence of clear instructional goals, appropriate learning resources, well-structured teaching processes, and positive learning outcomes. Overall, the results point to a coherent curriculum design and a generally supportive teaching–learning environment.

From the **context** perspective, both courses were aligned with students' academic and professional needs, indicating that the program was relevant to its intended purpose. In terms of **input**, the findings suggest that the courses were supported by suitable materials, assessment procedures, and digital learning tools, although ESP-2 appeared to involve slightly greater complexity due to its more applied and profession-ori-

ented focus. Regarding **process**, both courses were perceived as organized, clear, and supportive, with positive responses toward instruction, classroom management, and formative feedback. However, ESP-1 received slightly stronger evaluations in some areas, suggesting that students may have found its more foundational content easier to follow than the more demanding structure of ESP-2. From the **product** dimension, the results reveal a clear developmental progression: ESP-1 mainly strengthened foundational academic and disciplinary English skills, whereas ESP-2 extended these into more applied, profession-related competencies.

At the same time, the evaluation identified a common area requiring further improvement across both courses. Speaking performance, teamwork, and interactive communication were comparatively less developed than other outcome areas, indicating the need for more collaborative, discussion-based, and practice-oriented learning activities. Strengthening these aspects would help create a more balanced ESP learning experience and further enhance students' communicative competence in professional contexts.

In conclusion, the findings confirm that ESP-1 and ESP-2 function as complementary stages within a coherent ESP curriculum. More broadly, the study highlights the value of the CIPP model as a systematic and comprehensive framework for evaluating ESP course implementation, identifying strengths and limitations, and informing evidence-based curriculum improvement.

Recommendations

The findings suggest several practical recommendations for improving ESP-1 and ESP-2. First, both courses should place greater emphasis on speaking, teamwork, and interactive communication through more discussion-based, collaborative, and practice-oriented activities. Second, ESP-2 may require additional instructional support, such as clearer guidance and more structured practice, to help students manage its more applied and professionally oriented content. Third, the current developmental progression between ESP-1 and ESP-2 should be maintained so that foundational skills are systematically extended into profession-related applications. Finally, future evaluations should continue to use systematic frameworks such as the CIPP model to support ongoing evidence-based curriculum improvement.

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